

Targeting HIV-1 integrase and LEDGF/p75 for drug development using computational approaches

U. Panwar^{1*}, S.K. Singh ¹

¹ Alagappa University, Department of Bioinformatics, Karaikudi, Tamilnadu, India.

Email: umeshpanwar07@gmail.com

Abstract:

Lacking potent drugs against HIV-1 cost millions of lives today. Since rapid emergence of drug resistance demands development of effective inhibitors. As HIV-1 integrase requires LEDGF/p75 cellular cofactor to accomplish the replication process. LEDGF/p75 directly states lentiviral integration. Since, rapid emergence of drug resistance demands development of potent inhibitors. Thus, we have applied an virtual screening approach followed by molecular docking, binding free energy and dynamics studies to identify a novel inhibitor to switch off the protein-protein interaction between IN-LEDGF/p75. Herein the identified compound could be a effective agents to cure viral infection.

Keywords:

Anti-HIV, IN-LEDGF/p75 interaction, Virtual Screening, Molecular Docking and Dynamics.

Figure 1: The representation of protein-protein interaction between HIV-1 integrase and LEDGF/p75.

References:

1. Christ, F., Debyser, Z. (2013) The LEDGF/p75 integrase interaction, a novel target for anti-HIV therapy. *Virology.*, 435,102-109.
2. Pommier, Y., Johnson, A.A., Marchand, C. (2005) Integrase inhibitors to treat HIV/AIDS. *Nat. Rev. Drug. Discov.*, ;4, 236-48.